

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS FOR INTEGRATING TRADITIONAL AND RENEWABLE ENERGY IN VIETNAM: THE ROLE OF PUMPED STORAGE HYDROPOWER

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ABSTRACT

As the world strives to limit global warming to below 2 degrees Celsius under the Paris Agreement, the transition to renewable energy has become imperative, especially for Vietnam, which is shifting towards wind and solar power to meet international environmental commitments. However, integrating traditional and renewable energy into the national grid poses significant challenges, including the intermittent nature of renewables, grid stability issues, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient energy storage.

To address these challenges, several key solutions are proposed: regulating the dispatch of existing hydropower, developing energy storage systems like pumped storage hydropower (PSP), creating suitable investment models, upgrading grid infrastructure with smart technologies, providing financial support for renewable projects, refining the regulatory framework, and training skilled personnel.

This study examines the role of PSP in Vietnam's renewable energy transition, focusing on the one specifically PSP as a case study (considering as Kim Son - Thuong Song Tri PSP project with capacity over 300 MW). By analyzing its technical, financial, regulatory, and environmental aspects, the research aims to clarify PSP's contributions and propose effective integration strategies for traditional and renewable energy sources. The findings underscore PSH's potential to enhance

grid reliability while highlighting challenges in investment models and policy support, offering valuable insights for optimizing energy storage and renewable investments in Vietnam.

PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Vietnam's energy sector is at a critical juncture as it seeks to balance traditional energy sources with the increasing share of renewable energy in the power grid. Wind and solar power, while promising, are inherently intermittent and introduce volatility into the grid. To meet both national energy demands and international climate commitments under COP26, some reliable form of energy storage is needed. Pumped Storage Hydropower (PSP) emerges as one of viable solutions, helping to mitigate the instability caused by fluctuating renewable energy production.

This study investigates the role of PSP in Vietnam's energy system, with a focus on the one specifically PSP project. Which offers a practical example of how PSP can contribute to grid stability and the integration of renewable energy sources and which model investment can be chose. Additionally, the research addresses key challenges such as high capital costs, regulatory issues, and environmental impacts, offering solutions that can be applied to future PSP projects in Vietnam.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This research employs a case study methodology focus on the one specifically PSP project (capacity over 300 MW). This case was selected for its significance in the broader context of Vietnam's renewable energy integration strategy. The study involves the following methods:

- Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including owner, project engineers, policymakers, and experts in energy systems, to gain insights into the technical, financial and models investment, and regulatory dimensions of the project.
- Document analysis of technical reports, energy policy documents, and environmental impact assessments to understand the operational challenges and legal framework of the project.
- Field observations to gather qualitative data on the physical infrastructure and operational procedures of the PSP project.
- Considering Quantitative analysis of power grid data, including fluctuations in renewable energy generation and the role of PSP in stabilizing the grid.

The combination of qualitative and quantitative data ensures a comprehensive understanding of both the theoretical and practical implications of PSP in Vietnam's energy landscape.

FINDINGS

Preliminary results from the analysis suggest that Pumped Storage Hydropower plays a crucial role in stabilizing the grid, particularly during periods of peak and off-peak demand. Or PSP can also act together with unstable renewable energy (from wind and solar) to create an energy mix to supply the grid in a stable and reliable manner.

The One specifically PSP project can provide effective in managing the intermittency of wind and solar energy, storing excess energy during high production times and releasing it when needed. Initial findings indicate that, PSP projects combine with renewable energy projects can significantly reduce CO2 emissions by replacing coal-fired plants, even during peak demand hours.

However, the study also reveals several challenges, particularly high initial investment costs and regulatory complexities. Policymakers and investors alike cite the need for more government incentives and streamlined approval processes to make PSP projects more financially viable.

DETAIL FINDINGS

TECHNICAL AND OPERATIONAL INSIGHTS

The Specifically PSP project has calculated to demonstrate success in balancing the energy load on the national grid, particularly during times when renewable sources like wind and solar are either overproducing or underperforming.

The project's storage capabilities allow for excess renewable energy to be stored during the day and discharged during the night, effectively reducing the strain on the grid. This PSP project can also act together with unstable renewable energy (from wind and solar) projects (considering invest a float solar at a reservoir) to create an energy mix to supply the grid in a stable and reliable manner.

FINANCIAL AND CHALLENGES

Currently, Vietnam's grid system is not strong enough to fully integrate renewable energy on a large scale. As renewable energy increases to gradually replace coal-fired thermal power, the grid must not only transmit electricity from production sources to consumers but also ensure the ability to transmit to energy storage facilities. This requires huge financial resources to build and upgrade appropriate

infrastructure. In addition, the development of smart grids also poses a significant challenge, requiring advanced technology and specialized human resources to operate the national grid system with the participation of both renewable energy and storage. Finally, challenges in planning and policy frameworks need to be addressed to ensure reasonable development, optimize resources and ensure the transition is sustainable.

In particular, PSP projects require large capital due to their complexity in terms of equipment technology, operating experience, policies on electricity purchase price from the grid for pumping and electricity sale price returned to the grid (about 80% compared to the amount of electricity to pump water to the upper lake) or unclear contract price for operating the entire project, leading to private investors not having enough basis to calculate investment efficiency as well as propose reasonable and effective investment models.

ENVIRONMENTAL AND SOCIAL CONSIDERATIONS

Pumped storage hydropower (PSP) generally has a relatively low environmental impact compared to conventional forms of energy, as it does not emit greenhouse gases and can support the integration of renewable energy. However, the environmental impact mainly comes from infrastructure construction, changes to aquatic ecosystems, and impacts on local landscapes.

For the **specifically** PSP project in question, by using existing irrigation reservoirs but with different elevations (**head water estimate as 70m**), the environmental impact is minimized by taking advantage of existing reservoirs, reducing the need to build new large reservoirs. However, the project can still have an impact on the environment during construction, so environmental protection measures are required to minimize the impact during operation.

More details

Figure 1. Energy transition achievements around the world (Source: Global energy transformation – A roadmap to 2050, IRENA, 2019)

Electricity generation by technology, 2000-2028

IEA. CC BY 4.0.

Notes: Electricity generation from wind and solar PV indicate potential generation including current curtailment rates. However, it does not project future curtailment of wind and solar PV, which may be significant in a few countries by 2028. The Curtailment section below discusses some of these recent trends.

Figure 2. The trend of renewable energy transition

Figure 3. Vietnam's power source structure according to the 8-nation power development plan issued in May 2023

Figure 4. Energy mix includes: wind power, solar power and pumped storage hydropower

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study contributes to the field of renewable energy integration by providing a detailed analysis of a real-world application of Pumped Storage Hydropower in Vietnam. By focusing on the one specifically PSP project, this research highlights the practical challenges and solutions for integrating PSP into the national grid in the context of the increasing need to increase the proportion of renewable energy in the grid.

This case study approach also fills a gap in the literature regarding the current grid capabilities and future growth potential, financial and investment models, regulatory, and social challenges that come with PSP projects, particularly in a developing nation like Vietnam.

The study offers actionable insights for policymakers on how to better facilitate PSP projects through regulatory reforms and incentive programs, while also providing a model for future energy storage projects in Vietnam and Southeast Asia also.

In addition, we can consider aspects including the following three items:

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

This study has the limitation of focusing on a specific case, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. However, the development of a specific project such as Kim Son - Thuong Song Tri PSP in the context of no completed and operational pumped storage hydropower projects in Vietnam can still provide valuable insights, serving as a reference for the implementation of other PSP projects in Vietnam and similar regions. Future research can be extended by comparing multiple PSP projects in different localities to confirm and extend these conclusions. The extension can also be applied to other types of energy storage.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings have significant implications for energy policymakers and investors. They highlight the need for targeted government policies that promote PSP as a key component of Vietnam's renewable energy transition strategy. Select and propose appropriate project development solutions and investment models, Public-private partnerships and financial mechanisms such as green bonds could be explored to address the high capital costs associated with PSP projects. The study also provides a blueprint for future energy storage projects, emphasizing the importance of aligning technical, financial, and regulatory strategies.

SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS

Successfully integrating PSP and renewable energy into the traditional energy grid could lead to enhanced energy access in rural areas, reduced carbon emissions, and overall economic development through more stable and reliable energy supplies. However, ensuring equitable land use and addressing community concerns about environmental impacts remain critical for the sustainable deployment of PSP projects.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Pumped Storage Hydropower offers a viable solution to the challenges of integrating renewable energy into Vietnam's grid. The Kim Son - Thuong Song Tri PSP project serves as a model for how PSP can be used to stabilize the grid, reduce emissions, and support the country's renewable energy transition.

While the project demonstrates the potential, role of PSP and Energy Storage projects (ESP), it also exposes financial, policy and regulatory challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize this potential. Future research could explore comparative analyses of PSP projects across different countries or regions to provide a broader understanding of how PSP and ESP can be integrated with renewable and traditional energy into the global energy landscape.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Achkari, O., & El Fadar, A. (2018). Renewable energy storage technologies – A review. In *Proceedings of Engineering and Technology (Vol. 35, pp. 69–79)*. Conférence Internationale en Automatique & Traitement de Signal (ATS-2018).
- Asian Development Bank. (2017). Pathways to low-carbon development for Viet Nam. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/389826/pathways-low-carbondevt-viet-nam.pdf>
- AFP. (2020). Gas boom risks ‘perfect storm’ for climate, economy: Report. <https://www.euractiv.com/section/energy-environment/news/gas-boom-risksperfect-storm-for-climate-economy-report/>
- Agora Energiewende & Instituto E+ Diálogos Energéticos. (2019). Report on the Brazilian power system. Berlin, Germany.
- Agora Energiewende. (2018). Energiewende 2030: The big picture. Megatrends, targets, strategies and a 10-point agenda for the second phase of Germany’s energy transition.
- Behabtu, H. A., Messagie, M., Coosemans, T., Berecibar, M., Fante, K. A., Kebede, A. A., & Van Mierlo, J. (2020). A review of energy storage technologies’ application potentials in renewable energy sources grid integration. *Sustainability*, 12(10511). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122410511>
- Bui Minh, T., Nguyen Ngoc, T., & Bui Van, H. (2023). Relationship between carbon emissions, economic growth, renewable energy consumption, foreign direct investment, and urban population in Vietnam. *Heliyon*, 9, e17544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17544>
- Deloitte Development LLC. (n.d.). *Energy storage: Tracking the technologies that will transform the power sector*.
- Do, L., & Phu, L. V. (2024). Residential electricity efficiency and implications for Vietnam’s clean energy transition. *The Electricity Journal*, 37(1), 107428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tej.2024.107428>
- Do, T. N., & Burke, P. J. (2024). Phasing out coal power in two major Southeast Asian thermal coal economies: Indonesia and Vietnam. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 80, 101451. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2024.101451>
- EASE-EERA. (2017). *Energy storage technology development roadmap*.
- Energy Watch Group. (2017). The shift from feed-in tariffs to tenders is hindering the transformation of the global energy supply to renewable energies. http://energywatchgroup.org/wpcontent/uploads/2018/01/2017-07-15-Policy_Paper_Feed-in_Tariff_Tenders.pdf
- Energy Watch Group. (2019). Global energy system based on 100% renewable energy: Power, heat, transport and desalination sectors. http://energywatchgroup.org/wpcontent/uploads/EWG_LUT_100RE_All_Sectors_Global_Report_2019.pdf
- Empresa de Pesquisa Energética. (2019). Terminais de regaseificação de GNL no Brasil: Panorama dos principais projetos. Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

- Gerner, F., Chattopadhyay, D., Bazilian, M., & Tran, K. H. (2017). Is pumped storage hydroelectric power right for Vietnam? *Live Wire, A Knowledge Note Series for the Energy & Extractives Global Practice, ESMAP, World Bank Group*. <https://documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documentsreports/documentdetail/1781621492316066770/is-pumped-storage-hydroelectric-power-right-for-vietnam>
- Gielen, D., Boshell, F., Saygin, D., Bazilian, M. D., & Wagner, N. (2019). The role of renewable energy in the global energy transformation. *Energy Strategy Reviews, 24*, 38-50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2019.01.006>
- IASS/Green ID. (2019). Future skills and job creation through renewable energy in Viet Nam: Assessing the co-benefits of decarbonising the power sector. Potsdam/Hanoi.
- ICAP. (2020). China - Beijing pilot ETS. https://icapcarbonaction.com/en/?option=com_etsmap&task=export&format=pdf&lay_out=list&systems%5B%5D=53
- International Council on Clean Transportation. (2020). Update on the global transition to electric vehicles through 2019. <https://theicct.org/sites/default/files/publications/update-global-EVstats-20200713-EN.pdf>
- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2023). Renewable Energy. https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/96d66a8b-d502-476b-ba94-54ffda84cf72/Renewables_2023.pdf
- International Energy Agency. (2019). Southeast Asia energy outlook. <https://www.iea.org/reports/southeast-asia-energy-outlook-2019>
- International Energy Agency. (2020). Global EV outlook 2020. <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-electric-car-sales-by-key-markets-2010-2020>
- International Energy Agency. (2018). World energy outlook 2018: Highlights. <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2018>
- International Energy Agency. (2019). The future of hydrogen: Seizing today's opportunities. <https://webstore.iea.org/the-future-of-hydrogen>
- IEA-RETD. (2016). RE transition – Transitioning to policy frameworks for cost-competitive renewables. Utrecht, IEA Technology Collaboration Programme for Renewable Energy Technology Deployment.
- Norton Rose Fulbright. (2019). Renewable energy snapshot: Viet Nam. <https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en/knowledge/publications/71562ac3/renewable-energy-snapshot-viet-nam>
- SolarV. (n.d.). Công nghệ lưu trữ năng lượng. <https://solarv.vn/cong-nghe-luu-tru-nang-luong>
- Timmons, D., Harris, J. M., & Roach, B. (2014). *The economics of renewable energy*. Global Development and Environment Institute, Tufts University. <http://ase.tufts.edu/gdae>
- United Nations Environment Programme & Frankfurt School. (2020). Global trends in renewable energy investment 2020. https://www.fs-unep-centre.org/wpcontent/uploads/2020/06/GTR_2020.pdf
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2016). The Paris Agreement.

- University of Technology Sydney. (2019). Renewable energy for Viet Nam. Institute for Sustainable Futures. <https://www.uts.edu.au/sites/default/files/article/downloads/Teske-MorrisNagrath-2019-Renewable-Energy-for-Viet-Nam-report.pdf>
- U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Fossil Energy. (2020, June 30). *Electricity storage technology review*.
- Wilke, M. (2011). Feed-in tariffs for renewable energy and WTO subsidy rules: An initial legal review.
- Zhang, M., Nie, J., Su, B., & Liu, L. (2024). An option game model applicable to multi-agent cooperation investment in energy storage projects. *Energy Economics*, 131, 107397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2024.107397>
- Zhang, W., Li, B., Xue, R., Wang, C., & Cao, W. (2021). A systematic bibliometric review of clean energy transition: Implications for low-carbon development. *PLOS ONE*, 16(12), e0261091. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261091>
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